

SIGNIFICANT ASPECTS OF TODAY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ORIENTAL MINIATURE ART OF THE XXI CENTURY

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the stages and trends of the development of Oriental miniature art of the XXI century were compared and seen under the pseudonym. The contribution of miniatures of today's period in miniature development was also briefly outlined.

Introduction: miniature (French: miniature; Latin: minium — red paint) — small volume (Miracle), whose artistic methods are extremely elegant, is told by works of Fine Art. Elegant miracle paintings created to embellish medieval manuscripts, as well as small-scale painting with bone, parchment, Maghreb fakes (Flint), metal, porcelain, sometimes household items (tamakidon, clock, ring, etc.), are also used as a miniature term. Miniatures were first worked from the head into the interior of books, devoting them to some epic, prose or nazmic work. Therefore, this type of art was closely related to The Art of Kitabat. Egypt was the oldest center in the formation of book miniatures in the arab East. Here it was done with a pencil or paint in a flat manner, similar to the images of ancient Egyptian tombs in the time of the Pharaohs. Miniatures are drawn on a large number of copies of the book of the dead. In the early Middle Ages, the miniature painting was continued by the Coptic-Egyptians who believed in Christianity. Book IV-VI miniature has become a leading type of Coptic art. One of the main centers of Syrian Arab miniature occupied by Arabs in the 7th century was seen in quality. Early arab miniature artists were Syrian Christians. Through them, the Babylonian tradition of illustration turned directly to the arab painting. ¹An example of this are miniatures drawn in the manuscript of Dioscrid "medicines" (Pharmacology²). 1badiy areas of miniature such as book and portrait miniature are widely known. In the miniature of the book, the paintings were made in color by hand with tempera, watercolors and other paints, directly processed into sheets of handwritten books, decorating the inside with patterns (Title, Title, sheet, etc.). Miniature has been known since ancient times. In pero with pale

1. ¹ Baymetov, B. B., & Sharipjonov, M. S. O. (2020). Development Of Students' Descriptive Competencies In Pencil Drawing Practice. *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations*, 2(08), 261-267.

2. ² Boltaboyevich, B. B., & Shokirjonugli, S. M. (2020). Formation of creative competences of the fine art future teachers describing geometrical forms (on sample of pencil drawing lessons). *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(5), 1996-2001.

paints on ancient Egyptian papyri, paintings were made in a painting manner with a flat surface.² The Last antique miniatures (IV-VI centuries) are notable for their forms and the fact that the state of light, air is given correctly. This further increased the artistic and compositional solution of the finished composition. Miniature art has also influenced other types of painting. This method reigned in Byzantine miniature (mainly religious manuscripts) until the 10th century.

In the Gothic miniature of the XIII-XV centuries, the desire for truthful expression of nature increased, images were highlighted with text, forms revived, landscape, interior, architectural frame³. Medieval Western miniature is characterized by a plurality of local schools. For example, we can say that a miniature has developed in Armenia (VI-VII centuries), Georgia (IX-X centuries), Russia (XIII century). In the Middle Ages, specific schools of miniature were formed in the East. In them, a number of schools stand out in the Arabic miniature, which is considered one of the first: Egypt, Syria, Iraq; Afghanistan, Central Asia, Azerbaijan, Iran, India all the decorations of the manuscript books are connected in harmony with each other; the linear rhythm, landscape, subtle harmony of colors determined their decorative structure. The concepts of shape, volume, color in them further increased the artistic solution of the composition. And these styles are also noticeable in miniature schools, which were formed in later times.

Even in miniature ³schools, which later took shape and became known around the world, the Basic Rules in the schools of the past period remained. That is, the presence of the working composition in two sizes, the absence of a bright shade is their common similarity. As we said at the beginning, classical miniature works developed in connection with the art of Kitabat. The famous epics, masnavids, which are considered masterpieces of artistic, nazmic poetry, miniatures worked out from the essence of the content of the ruboians have survived to this day. Here are some examples of such famous nazmic works. For Example: "Shahname" Of Firdavsi. A separate category is miniatures created to embellish the manuscripts of the works of Nizami, Khusrav Dextdavi, Alisher Navoi, Hamsa, Jami, Saadi, Hafiz Sheroziy and others. After Moni in the East as great musavvir, the names of Junaid Baghdad, Khoja Abdulhay, Mahmud Inkqalam, Gidhosiddin Naqosh, Mirak Naqash, Kamoliddin Bekhzad, Qasim Ali, Mahmud Muzahhib, Abdulla Musavvir, Basavan, Rizoyi Abbasiy and others were popular. During the Timurid period, it became a tradition to work miniatures on individual papers and draw murals from them. The work of the image (portrait) of individual individuals has progressed, in particular, in India, to a high level during the Baburid period. And we are not mistaken if we say that Kamoliddin Bekhzod, the founder of the herotus miniature school, laid the foundation for the portert miniature. His portraits " Shaybaniy Khan", " Alisher Navoi", " Hussein ⁴Boykaro", " Navoi and Boykaro " are still preserved. At the end of the XIV – beginning of the XV centuries, the Emir Timur statehood arose. During his military campaigns, Amir Timur brought science, art and crafts from the countries he occupied to Samarkand, creating conditions for them to live and create. According to the eastern authors, the founder of the

³ Amanullaev, A. A. (2022). CURRENT ISSUES IN THE TRAINING OF FUTURE TEACHERS OF FINE ARTS. ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603, 11(03), 1-3.

⁴ Amanullaev, A. A. (2022). CURRENT ISSUES IN THE TRAINING OF FUTURE TEACHERS OF FINE ARTS. ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603, 11(03), 1-3.

Timurid school in the Fine Arts is Ustod Gung (dumb), whose arrival exit is unknown. The name of his disciple Umdatul Musavvir (leader of the musavvirs) was Jahongir, a Bukhara Master famous in biloan. Master Jahongir mentored the famous Pir Sayyid Ahmad Tabrizi. And Kamoliddin Bekhzad learned the painting from this Pir Sayyid Ahmad Tabrizi.⁵ so Kamoliddin Behzod also founded the Herot miniature school. And under the influence of this school, other miniature schools later took shape. But it was after Kamoliddin Behzad that the level of the Herot miniature school was significantly reduced. Because the painting styles that came in from the West, combined with the Basic Rules of classical miniature, lost the original essence of miniature. We thought about the history of 6 miniatures. Let's now also talk a little about the characters in them. Selecting, copying, and learning to describe specific content leads to the application of some compositional schemes and epic hero⁵-specific characters in the form of a mold. For example, the Pharaoh hero Rustam is always depicted on a tiger's skin and a helmet made of his head, which is a sign of his unparalleled strength. Regardless of when and where it will be worked out, we will recognize from all other miniatures of its "Shahnameh" these signs. Another hero of firdavsi, Siyovush, is always depicted in white clothes, a symbol of purity. The main character of Jami's "Joseph and Zulayho" is surrounded by fire, a symbol of the prophesy of Joseph's head. Thus, the adjectives spoken in words. The stages of describing the image of a person in miniature are associated with the evolution of his figure in literature, as well as with the evolution of the entire book decoration system. As a result of the inspection of miniature schools of different eras, we learn this connection. At the end of the 13th and beginning of the 14th centuries, artists, like poets, describe the human czechra in accordance with the ideal of beauty ("Varka and Gulshah", XIV century) and turn it into a certain pattern of composition. In the 15th century, thanks to the genius of Kamoliddin Bekhzad, the image of a person acquired its value. In the kmposition, naturalness, proportionality arose, gestures varied, enriched, avoiding the previous hypocrisy, to which he was given a special place. New characters came up. Most of the heroes of Behzod's works were this simple Hall. An example of this is the " construction of the Havarnaq Castle " (Herat, late 15th century. Manuscript of the British Museum, London, 0 6810, C. Page 154.) we can get the composition. (Photo 1) note that all the heroes of this composition are ordinary working people. Their clothes are also depicted as the clothes of ordinary people. The composition reflects the construction process. The heroes in it are connected with each other without interruption. That is, there is no single image on Earth. BARC is portrayed in a state where human characters are engaged in some kind of work. In terms of form, the castle and the Earth occupied a large volume . And the sky will rise from it. And after them, people in a dynamic state who do not repeat one are shown asks. In the coloritic aspect, the fact that warm colors were brought to the fore further revealed the composition. By contrast to them,

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Pulatov D. S. Formation of Ancient Sculpture on the Territory of Uzbekistan //International Journal of Social Science Research ar 294.

Pulatov, Dilmurod Saymamutovich. "Formation of Ancient Sculpture on the Territory of Uzbekistan." *International Journal of Social Science Research and Review* (2022): 290-294. Pulatov, D. S.

(2022). Formation of Ancient Sculpture on the Territory of Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Social Science Research and Review*

we can get an image of the sky in light blue. In general, this composition fully complies with all the rules of classical miniature. Analyzing classical miniature works, we notice that they are simply not worked out. Each created work speaks its own essence of the era haida. We witness that that time has clearly revealed the images of man, his way of life. The fact that even the small details used in them were taken from real life increased the naturalness of the composition in nyana.. Thinking about the fine art of the past, we should dwell only on the word minityura, which is used a lot today, in part. This phrase was practically not used until the beginning of the XIX century. It has become a tradition to use "miniature" - a photograph that worked on a book (a miraculous image) or in relation to elegant images of a small size. The miniature in the image art of the peoples of the East, including Central Asia, also has its own examples. In this regard, the school of Herat "Niguristan"⁷ (Academy of Fine Arts), which has given rise to its unique samples and representatives of amazing⁸ art in the history of our Fine Arts, stands in the front lines within the schools of World Fine Arts. It was in this school that such a great artist as Kamoliddin Bekhzod matured. In order to more accurately understand the essence and content of this school, we need to analyze its Maana. When it comes to the phrase "niguristan", it must be said that it means nigors, Faces, Faces.⁷ The scientist Naim Norkulov reported that Boysunkur Mirzo Herot created the conference (Academy) of fine and Fine Arts. Khodja Giyosiddin Haravi, Amrshahiy vegetable, Mirak Naqash, Halil Mirzo Shahruhiy, Sultan Ibrahim, Sultanali Mashhad, Mavlon Ja'far Turbati were the organizers of Herat Academy. At the prestigious art school formed in Herat, Kamoliddin Bekhzad mentored dozens of artists. In general, the universality of Behzad's work is that he was able to create an immortal school. Inspired by his work, many artists such as Qasim Ali, Sultan Muhammad, Muzafar Ali, Yusuf Mullo, Rustam Ali, Mirsaid Ali, Mahmud Muzahhib and Abdullah served for the prosperity of miniature art and Kitabat art.

Conclusion: in our study of the miniature art of Central Asia, we can not help but pay attention to the art of painting of ancient Uzbekistan. The ancient art of painting belonging to the territory of Uzbekistan has its own invaluable examples. Of these, the role of Samarkand in Afrosiyab, Surkhondarya's childhood, Varakhsha in Bukhara, mural-colored images in Panjikent are noteworthy. In miniature, painting has its own nuances of work. It does not use color pespectiva, linear pespectiva, air pespectiva. With the art of medieval miniatures, the current era differs in the modern miniature art, development. In modern miniature art, various images and decorations are given in clothes in the image of people, silence is observed.

The work and study of composition in the genre of miniature is of great importance for the ability to see the beauties of nature, as well as for the development of aesthetic taste in young people. It can be an important factor in young people to awaken a sense of patriotism and look at the heritage of ancestors with national pride. This, in turn, will help the younger

⁶ Pulatov, D. S. (2022). Formation of Ancient Sculpture on the Territory of Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Social Science Research and Review*, 5(7), 290-294.

⁷ Ruzinov, B. A. (2023). TASVIRIY SAN'AT RIVOJLANISH TARIXI VA BUGUNGI KUNDAGI AHAMIYATLI JIHATLARINI O'RGANISH VA TAXLIL QILISH. MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH, 2(19), 1-8.

⁸ Pulatov, Dilmurod Saymamutovich. "Formation of Ancient Sculpture on the Territory of Uzbekistan." *International Journal of Social Science Research and Review* 5.7 (2022): 290-294.

generation to take a good step into the future, expressing the right attitude to the past. Today, miniature art has its place in making the Land of Uzbekistan more beautiful and beautiful, as well as in raising the future generation to be harmonious people.

APPLICATION

A.Navoi epic "Hamsa"
287x560

A.Navoi epic "Hamsa"Farhod x Shirin
383x595

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